

PROJECT COLDSPARK®

Revolutionizing **hydrogen production** with **ColdSpark®** from **biomethane**

Risavika base in Tananger, Norway

Risavika base is an area that serves Northern Europe's largest oil and gas

Offshore base operations

The terminal in Risavika (and Dusavika) is a well-established port area for offshore base operations

LNG facility

Risavika LNG is a medium-scale LNG facility located in Risavika (2010). The facility has an annual production capacity of 300,000 tonnes of LNG, equivalent to the energy needs of two cities

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www.coldspark.eu

Funded by
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A novel approach to
sustainable hydrogen
production

ColdSpark is created on SEID's 25 years of experience with Non-Thermal Plasma and high voltage power systems.

Project ColdSpark®

ColdSpark® is a 42-month Horizon Europe (HE) project launched in June 2022. It will validate a novel cold plasma (non-thermal plasma) technology to produce hydrogen, alongside high-value carbon, at an industrial scale from methane.

Two major sources of **HYDROGEN** on earth:

*Theoretical minimum amount

Waste to values - circular and sustainable?

Waste > Biogas > Hydrogen and Solid Carbon > Values

- ✓ Cost-competitive, environmental-friendly Hydrogen from biogas
- ✓ The reactor's modular design enables low CAPEX and OPEX, resulting in increased flexibility and scalability compared to other production techniques (SMR/electrolysis).
- ✓ Produced by clean energy
- ✓ The novel plasma reactor will utilize both natural gas and biomethane.

ULTRA LOW CO₂ or other greenhouse gases

A low energy cost without the need for catalysts and water, makes this solution the most cost-competitive, environment friendly, and less complex to implement

✓ Ultra low-carbon hydrogen

✓ Waste into value

✓ High energy efficiency